

Unveiling the Health Risk of Air Pollution : A Statistical Analysis of Urban Jaipur

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Abstract

The contamination of the indoor and outdoor environment by any physico-chemical or biological source that transforms the natural characteristics of the atmosphere is Air pollution. Its enhanced limit in megacities posing health risks for city dwellers. Disease like bronchitis and infections of lungs are generally the aftermaths of air pollution. Indian cities at par the range of 267 in terms of Air Quality Index (AQI) are more than twenty and have been categorised as most polluted in the world. Making the permissible limit accessible to the city dwellers has remained a grave concern to the policy framers. The research unveils the health risk pertaining to the polluted air in the city of Jaipur, the capital of Rajasthan. The statistical analysis of AQI at different urban locality has been presented to justify the objective of the research activity. Moreover the paper aims to summarize health impact of air pollution in Jaipur city owing to the degradation of AQI. The task incorporates collating the literature, historical, social and geographical data for an integrated understanding of present scenario of air pollution in urban domain of Jaipur city.

It is worth mentioning here that VKI and RIICO office area North contain more air pollution than other urban dwelling areas.

Keywords Air Quality Index, Urban, Contamination, Air pollution, Carbon monoxide.

Introduction

The Indian cities are engulfed with high air pollution as most of the urban dwellers are experiencing air pollutant levels above the permissible limit. The continuous emissions from both anthropogenic as well as natural sources causing high Particulate Matter concentration posing adverse human health impacts. This highlights the necessity of continuous monitoring of air pollutants. As per Central Pollution Control Board (CPCB) and World Health Organisation (WHO), the rapid urbanization has led to the significant degradation of Air Quality Index (AQI) in most of the Indian cities with the air quality above the permissible limit. Moreover the daily and annual average values are rising at an alarming rate for most of the gaseous pollutants in Indian cities. The urban health has been deteriorated most by the air pollution related diseases being identified in India recently. The health issues linked with air pollution is a matter of concern specially for Indian capital cities. In India, the outdoor air pollution has become fifth eminent reason of death after high blood pressure, indoor air pollution, poor nutrition and tobacco smoking in 2015 causing about 0.62 million premature excess number of death cases.

Air pollution is linked with short term, medium or long term impacts on human health. Irritation to eyes, throat, and nose, and some respiratory infections such as pneumonia and bronchitis are placed under short term impact while long term air pollution impacts involve chronic respiratory diseases, heart related problems, lung cancer, and even damage to the brain, liver, kidneys, or nerves. The cities now days counter the problem of premature mortality and hospitalization for respiratory and post respiratory illnesses. Intensification of biomass and biofuel burning emissions during post-monsoon and wintertime have implications to deeper penetration and higher mass deposition fraction of fine-particles in the thoracic and pulmonary areas. Children, elderly people and pregnant women are more prone to health risks owing to air pollutants.

The Jaipur city has been a natural choice to find out the health impact of air quality as the research area is one of the earliest planned cities of modern India. Jaipur is an economically vibrant city. Tourism, trade and commerce and local handicrafts industries are the key strengths of the city. Several facilities are provided by the capital city like housing, transportation, communication, education and recreation. This makes the capital city a more attractive place for immigrants. The decade of 1951-61 and onwards also witnessed the setting up of certain major industries in industrial side such as Bais Godown and industrial areas such as Jhalana, Malviya Nagar, Vishwakarma and Kartarpura, Sudarshanpura, EPIP at Sitapura, Sanganer, Kanakpura, Kukas, Mahindra SEZ and RIICO industrial area. Thus Jaipur provided an incentive for better jobs to the people living in the neighbouring suburbs and rural areas. Resultantly, people who came to Jaipur for job opportunities ultimately settled with their families in the city. Hence the process of urbanization is inevitable due to which the municipal extension to house the ever growing population becomes a necessity. The aftermath of this expansion is the one of many reasons for the deterioration of sustainability of urban environment.

The city's rapid population growth and rising vehicle emissions have significantly impacted its air quality, leading to health concerns for both residents and the large commuting population. Addressing air quality issues in Jaipur city is therefore vital not only for public health but also for fostering a healthier and more supportive global sustainable tourism, benefiting urban dwellers, domestic and foreigners comprehensively. Jaipur has a monsoon-influenced hot semi-arid climate with long extremely hot summers and short, mild to warm winters. These conditions contribute to high concentrations of particulate matter, particularly during summer and winter when thermal inversion traps pollutants closer to the ground.

Objective of study

To have an insight of the impact of air pollution on the health of urban dwellers.

Review of Literature

Roy et al., (2001). The people residing in Kolkata city were facing seven times higher burden on their lungs due to air pollution as compared to their rural counterparts and about 47% of Kolkata's residents were suffering from lower respiratory tract symptoms.

H Bayram, et al. (2002). Background Although epidemiological as well as in vivo exposure studies suggest that ozone (O₃) and nitrogen dioxide (NO₂) may play a role in airway diseases such as asthma.

Chan, (2003). Referred specifically to the commuter exposure inside a vehicle, most people like to close the windows and switch on the air-conditioning system to avoid directly breathing the polluted air. However a number of questions arise: firstly, indoor air is simply an extension of that outdoor.

Dales et al. (2004). Sudden infant death syndrome (SIDS) affects 1 in 1000 live births and is the most common cause of infant death after the perinatal period.

Ghose et al., (2005). Various epidemiological studies conducted in this concern states that poor quality of air poses significant risk to human health creating problems such as decreased lung function, respiratory symptoms and increased asthma incidence, allergy, and cardio-respiratory illness.

Gehring et al. (2006). Living close to major roads or highways has been suggested to almost double the risk of dying from cardiopulmonary causes.

Gehring et al. (2006). Long-term exposure to ambient air pollution and cardiopulmonary mortality in women.

Hajat et al. (2007). There is growing concern that moderate levels of outdoor air pollution may be associated with infant mortality, representing substantial loss of life-years.

Beelen, R. M. J. (2008). Studied effects of long-term exposure to traffic-related air pollution on mortality and lung cancer.

Mukhopadhyay, (2009). The health issues such as genetic changes, impaired liver function, hematological abnormalities, and neurobehavioral problems were also associated with air pollution especially for the people exposed to higher vehicular emissions. These include traffic policeman, auto, and taxi drivers and roadside hawkers.

Canova et al. (2010). Carbon monoxide pollution is associated with decreased lung function in asthmatic adults.

(OECD, 2014). In India, about 0.62 million in 2005 and 0.69 million in 2010 premature death cases have occurred due to outdoor air pollution.

Vinikoor-Imler et al. (2015) performed an exploratory analysis of ozone and fine particulate matter concentrations during early pregnancy and multiple types of birth defects.

(Maji et al., 2016). Although gaseous air pollutants such as NO₂ and SO₂ are matter of increasing concern for human health, but particulate matter was observed as prominent reason for air pollution related mortality and morbidity rather than gaseous pollutants.

Haque and Singh,(2017) Chronic obstructive pulmonary diseases, influenza, bronchitis, asthma, upper track respiratory infection, and acute respiratory infections were some other health impacts observed for Indian cities due to air pollution.

Liu et al., 2019, (2018) There is much evidence that both acute and chronic exposure to air pollution, especially coarse and fine particulates, increases the morbidity and mortality of the population.

Zhang et al., (2019), In LDCs with limited access to clean cooking fuels and ventilation technologies, reliance on biomass fuels for cooking and heating exposures households lead to high levels of indoor air pollution.

GAHP, (2020). According to the Lancet Report, pollution costs the global economy \$4.6 trillion per year, corresponding to 6.2% of global economic output.

Mostafavi et al., (2021). About 91% of world's population has been found to be residing in areas with air quality higher than permissible limits according to WHO.

Marquès and Domingo (2022) Suggested that air pollution may be linked to COVID-19 outcomes

Aguilera et al., 2023; Jones et al., (2023).Biomass fuels held responsible for indoor air pollution and contributing to respirator disease, low birth weights and other health problems.

J Infante-Amate, E Aguilera (2024)One of the main challenges facing our society is to decouple levels of well-being from environmental impacts, particularly greenhouse gas emissions (GHGe). Historical knowledge can provide crucial information on the feasibility of achieving this goal

Methodology

City municipal corporation boundary is generated with Arc GIS 10.2 and Erdas Imagine 2011. Initially Google Earth application followed by LISS-4 /PAN -temporal and multi-resolution satellite data for the interpretation of expansion of area locations pertaining to 2024.Both secondary and primary data has been used.

Table: 1

Primary Information / data		Field Schedule	
Secondary Information / data		Source Uses	
1.	Published data of Govt. of India & Govt. of Rajasthan.	The Statistical Abstract (GOI & GOR) 2010-2024	Spatial distribution of sites
2.	Rajasthan Govt. Survey Report(GOI), 2001, 2011, 2018	Govt. of Rajasthan	For Air Quality Index analysis.
3.	Data records of AQL. (Jaipur Greater)	Official Ward Centers.	For quantification of grim situation to humans, and Significance.
	Structured no probability sampling method applied.		

Study Area

Figure1: Study area (Source: JDA, 1990 & JDA, 2011)

Jaipur is situated amidst the Aravali hill ranges at an altitude of about 430 metres MSL and lies on latitude $26^{\circ}55'$ north and longitude $75^{\circ}50'$. Koeppen climate classification BSh. The hill ranges girdle the city from three sides, thus leaving only the southern region for further expansion. Jaipur is directly linked with several large towns inside and outside Rajasthan by road, rail and air. It is an important railway junction on the Delhi-Ahmedabad railway line. Besides, National Highways Eight and Eleven run through the city of Jaipur, while Highway One links Jaipur with Kota- the industrial city of Rajasthan.

The climate of the city is dry and the temperature fluctuates between 25°C TO 41°C in summer and between 6.5°C to 25°C in winter. The average annual rainfall is 62cm. While the average humidity in July is 80%. This approximately 240 years old city has been known for its splendid architecture, christened as Pink City.

Expansion of the City

The city has been gradually expanding its municipal frontiers to meet the demand of the increasing population. It is obvious that the walled city can no more provide additional housing facilities to a very large number of people as its area is restricted by the enclosing wall. Resultantly many new colonies have come up in the outlying areas.